

THE CROSS-LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF SUGGESTION SPEECH ACT BASED ON JIANG'S TAXONOMY IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LITERARY WORKS

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Suggestions are a type of directive speech act that aim to guide the hearer toward a future course of action for their benefit or shared interest. The way suggestions are expressed varies significantly across languages and cultures, reflecting sociopragmatic norms and degrees of directness. This study applies Jiang's (2006) taxonomy of suggestions to examine and compare suggestion strategies in English, Uzbek and Karakalpak using authentic literary dialogues as data. The aim is to identify patterns of directness, conventionality and implicitness that characterize each language.

The analysis draws on examples from conversations in three literary works:

- "Death of a Salesman" (English, Arthur Miller)
- "Oq kema" (Uzbek, Chingiz Aytmatov)
- "Ashiq bolmağan kim bar" (Karakalpak, Muratbay Nızanov)

A total of 10 suggestion expressions per language were selected. Jiang's taxonomy was used as the analytic framework, classifying suggestions into:

- Direct (e.g., imperatives),
- Conventionally indirect (e.g., interrogatives or modal-based forms),
- Non-conventionally indirect (e.g., hints, implicit cues).

Each example was coded and analyzed according to its level of explicitness and formal structure.

The analysis of the English dialogues in Death of a Salesman reveals three instances of direct suggestions, six instances of conventionally indirect suggestions, and one instance of a non-conventionally indirect suggestion.

1. Direct Suggestions (3 examples):

- Go to your boss and tell him the truth.
- Take a rest, Dad.
- Let's go for a walk, Dad.

2. Conventionally Indirect Suggestions (6 examples):

- Why don't you go to Alaska?
- Would you consider starting your own business?
- You might talk to Charley.

3. Non-conventionally Indirect Suggestions (1 example):

- You could make something of yourself, Biff.

The Uzbek instances extracted from novel “Oq kema” include five cases of direct suggestions, four cases of conventionally indirect suggestions, and one case of a non-conventionally indirect suggestion.

1. Direct Suggestions (5 examples):

- Keling choy ichamiz.
- Bolaga kitob olib beraylik.
- Keling, bugun daryo bo'yiga boraylik.

2. Conventionally Indirect Suggestions (4 examples):

- Mo'min bobo, siz aytib bergan afsonani yozib olaylikmi?
- Orolpo'sh, endi dam olsangizchi?
- Ertalabdan birga yursakchi?

3. Non-conventionally Indirect Suggestions (1 example):

- Orolpo'sh, siz bolaga mehr ko'rsating.

The Karakalpak examples, drawn from the novel “Ashiq bolmağan kim bar” comprise six instances of direct suggestions, three instances of conventionally indirect suggestions, and one instance of a non-conventionally indirect suggestion.

1. Direct Suggestions (6 examples):

- Ju'r sag'an bir zat ko'rsetemen.
- Atin Qo'shqarbay qo'yag'o'y meni tın'lasan'.
- Ju'r inim bu'gin jengen' gu'nji mayg'a palaw asıp atır.

2. Conventionally Indirect Suggestions (3 examples):

- Bolmasa men keyinirek keleyin be?
- O'rnin'izg'a jatın'.
- İnim sen basqa ju'mısqa o'teg'o'.

3. Non-conventionally Indirect Suggestions (1 example):

- Jaqsi niyet qılın'!

The distribution of suggestion types reflects both linguistic structure and cultural norms:

➤ English tends to favor conventionally indirect forms, often using questions with modals (“Why don’t you...?”, “Would you...?”), which aligns with Anglo-American politeness norms that value indirectness and face-saving strategies.

➤ Uzbek shows a balanced use of direct and conventional forms, suggesting an openness to cooperative and community-centered communication. Direct forms like “Keling choy ichamiz” carry warmth rather than force.

➤ Karakalpak leans more toward direct suggestions, often using imperative or declarative structures softened by cultural expressions of closeness or solidarity. This directness may reflect oral traditions and pragmatic norms of suggestion within kin-based or familiar contexts.

Across all three languages, non-conventionally indirect suggestions are rare, reinforcing Jiang’s observation that such forms are less frequent due to their ambiguity.

This cross-linguistic analysis confirms that suggestion strategies vary in degree of directness and formality, shaped by pragmatic preferences and cultural expectations. While English favors conventionally indirect suggestions, Uzbek blends directness with politeness, and Karakalpak tends toward direct, contextually grounded expressions. Jiang’s taxonomy proves effective in capturing these nuances, offering a clear framework for comparative pragmatic study

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